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Tentative Title: Food as a marker of identity for Kashmiri Pandits

For displaced communities, food serves as a memory of loss and nostalgia. The Kashmiri Pandits are one such community. In January 1990, large numbers of the Kashmiri Pandits began leaving the valley in a bid for survival following the assassination of multiple Hindu Pandits. It is estimated that a total of 150,000 Kashmiri Pandits left the Kashmir Valley in this exodus and settled into refugee camps in Jammu and Delhi. On this alien land, they continue to carry with them their flavours and culinary traditions to preserve their cultural heritage.

Yet, even as these migrants continue to follow their culinary tradition, their displacement to a new geographical location has led to substituted ingredients depending on the resources available to them. In this regard, what might seem like purely an act of preservation¹ results in renewal, not because the community seeks a break from traditions, but because survival in an unfamiliar land requires practical adjustments to ingredients and culinary technique.

For this purpose, it is essential to understand that assimilation and renewal are two distinct but simultaneous and interconnected processes. Assimilation refers to the potential loss of traditions and distinctiveness by adopting the practices of a dominant culture. This instils fear among Kashmiri Pandits that their cultural identity could be erased. In response to this fear, the community take conscious efforts to preserve their native cuisines. This is evident from the ceremonial cooking of dishes such as *gade batta* or *tschor tschot* during *Herath*. These efforts give birth to renewal, that is, the recreation of native cuisines through substituted ingredients and slightly modified techniques, ensuring continuity even amidst change.

Based on preliminary research, the following are some questions we are interested in exploring in greater depth through this paper.

- i. How did Kashmiri Pandit cuisines function within festivities and communal events preceding the exodus in the late 20th century?
- ii. Understanding how traditional daily practices and household rituals shaped the foodways of the Kashmiri Pandits and how they contribute to their cultural identity.

- iii. What are the changes visible in the culinary practices of the Kashmiri Pandits following the exodus? What factors have contributed to these transformations?

(Though these are a few of our research interests at the moment, but can be modified during the research process.)

The methodology will follow a mixture of both primary and secondary resources to address the research questions. It seeks to critically engage with literary texts and research articles. Cookbooks, archival and oral history records drawn from *Kashmir Records* will also be examined.

Though there are already existing studies on culinary traditions of Kashmiri Pandits. Building upon it, we will investigate how food acts as a marker of identity for Kashmiri Pandits residing in Jammu.

A comparative and thematic study would be done to trace the continuities and changes in the cuisines of Kashmiri Pandits since their displacement from the Kashmir Valley. While engaging with the cookbooks, we will analyse recipes as well as narratives, contexts, and instructions to understand the transmission of culinary knowledge. In addition, YouTube channels, social media pages, and cook shows will be carefully examined to observe how these cuisines are prepared in modern times and whether these sources indicate how they were practised historically, particularly in the late 20th century.

The community of Kashmiri Pandits living in Jammu is itself heterogeneous, and culinary practices may vary within households. However, this paper focuses primarily on the largely common culinary practices.

Due to time and resource constraints, this paper constitutes a micro-study of Kashmiri Pandits' cultural identity in Jammu, especially in reference to their cuisine, and does not seek to represent the community in its entirety. Moreover, the reliance on translated cookbooks, literature, YouTube channels, and cook shows may introduce interpretive barriers, as language and translation may affect the understanding of traditional practices.

Keywords: Kashmiri Pandits, Culinary Practices, Assimilation, Preservation, Renewal

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